

1 **TRPC1 is a signature transcriptional feature of human epilepsy and regulates electrical activity in**
2 **the brain.**

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7 Our goal is reduction or elimination of morbidity and mortality from disease in humans. Cancer and heart
8 disease are the two most common sources of mortality in humans. We identified a gene whose product is
9 useful in universal detection of solid tumors before dissemination and pioneered quantitative determination
10 of therapeutic vulnerabilities to prevent treatment resistant cancer.

11 Maladies that affect the brain, including psychiatric and neurologic conditions, are a major source of
12 human morbidity. Epilepsy is a serious condition associated with abnormal electrical activity that results in
13 seizures (1). Some cases of epilepsy are treatment resistant. We describe here transient receptor
14 potential cation channel subfamily C member 1, encoded by *TRPC1* as an essential element of the
15 epilepsy gene expression signature in the human brain. Genetic and systems biological studies
16 demonstrate that TRPC1 regulates gene expression important for electrical activity in the brain.
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We measured total transcription in the healthy and epileptic brain to discover the most significant expression changes in the brains of humans with the seizure disorder epilepsy.

Results

Figure 1: TRPC1 is a signature transcriptional feature of the brain in epilepsy.

GSE134697

n=2 neocortex (healthy control humans)

n=17 neocortex (humans with mesial temporal lobe epilepsy)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
7220	2.80E-03	0.1141	-2.989202	-3.41E-01	653.58	TRPC1	388/23079	98.3

GSE168375

n=12 cerebral cortex astrocytes; healthy individuals (control)

n=31 cerebral cortex astrocytes; epilepsy

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
7220	5.41E-02	0.1526	-1.926223	-2.94E-01	777.72	TRPC1	4671/17680	73.6

Analysis of whole transcription in the human brain, in the neocortex and in cerebral cortex astrocytes, demonstrated that induction of TRPC1 expression was a fundamental aspect of the epilepsy gene expression signature.

Next we utilized a systems biological method to identify gene products that interact with TRPC1 at the level of gene expression by studying transcriptional co-regulation across multiple human cellular contexts (Figure 2). We studied TRPC co-regulation in the brain.

Figure 2: TRPC1 is transcriptionally co-regulated with voltage-gated channels.

1 Query genes:

2 Query Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value
TRPC1	7220	-3.2000	0.0029

3 Coexpressed genes (out of 17856 co-regulated genes transcriptome-wide):

4 :

5 Rank	Query	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score/p-value	Description	%Co-reg
6 134	KCNT2	343450	1.1659 0.0034	potassium channel, subfamily T, member 2	99.2
7 345	CLCN3	1182	1.0333 0.0295	chloride channel, voltage-sensitive 3	98.1
8 611	VDAC3	7419	0.9408 0.1094	voltage-dependent anion channel 3	96.5
9 705	SCN2A	6326	0.9156 0.0161	sodium channel, voltage-gated, type II, alpha subunit	96.1
830	KCND2	3751	0.8792 0.0085	potassium voltage-gated channel, Shal-related subfamily, member 2	95.4
967	CLCN4	1183	0.8457 0.0089	chloride channel, voltage-sensitive 4	94.6

10 The data indicated that TRPC1 was regulated with a network of voltage-gated channels in the brain (Figure 2)..

11 Finally, we conducted loss-of-function experimentation by measuring total transcription following
12 depletion of TRPC1 in human cells (Figure 3).

13 **Figure 3: Silencing of TRPC1 in human cells results in alterations in expression of voltage-gated channels.**

14 GSE77616

15 *n*=6 human primary aortic smooth muscle cells (control; transfected with empty silencing vector)

16 *n*=6 human primary aortic smooth muscle cells with shTRPC1 (TRPC1 silencing)

17 GSE77618

18 *n*=6 Huh7 human cells (control; transfected with empty silencing vector)

19 *n*=6 Huh7 human cells with shTRPC1 (TRPC1 silencing)

20 IIla. Depletion of TRPC1 results in loss of expression of KCND3, a potassium voltage-gated channel.

21 ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
22 ILMN_1727438	9.99e-02	1.77	-4.25993	3.56e-01	KCND3	6624/44803	85.2
ILMN_1752012	0.0014353	3.95	-0.9937	6.10e-01	KCND3	177/47314	99.6

24 IIlb. Depletion of TRPC1 results in enhanced expression of SCN1B, a potassium voltage-gated channel.

25 ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
26 ILMN_1801302	2.07e-01	-1.33	-4.76593	-2.79e-01	SCN1B	12528/48803	74.3
ILMN_1801302	0.0109553	-2.93	-2.6022	-5.31e-01	SCN1B	1171/47314	97.5

1 Ilc. Depletion of TRPC1 results in loss of expression of ENKUR, a TRPC channel-interacting protein.

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ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
3 ILMN_1735292	6.86e-02	1.99	-3.98602	2.85e-01	ENKUR	4754/48803	90.3
4 ILMN_1735292	0.0522388	2.12	-3.8382	4.30e-01	ENKUR	4643/47314	90.2

5 **Discussion**

6 We discovered and described here a role for TRPC1 in human epilepsy, at least in part through its
7 ability to regulate gene expression important for conducting electricity in the brain.

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